

PREPARATION OF PUMPKIN (CUCURBITA L) FROM THE RAW MATERIALS OF DIFFERENT VARIETIES

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Abstract. *The scientific article developed the technology of processing various varieties and hybrids of pumpkin in sugar syrup, semi-finished products are dried in a drying cabinet at a temperature of 40-50 0C, and finished products are processed in sugar powder.*

Keywords: *pumpkin variety, pumpkin slice, sugar syrup, color scale, drying, heat, temperature.*

Relevance of the topic.

The introduction of new technologies, ideas, and the introduction of new technologies, ideas into the field of processing and storage of agricultural products is one of the urgent issues of today. Analyzing optimal options for drying pumpkin slices in food industry enterprises and introducing them to production, as well as justifying the parameters and operating modes of drying pumpkin plants using infrared light.

Butler F1, Bakhodir, Ispanskaya 73, Kashgarskaya 1644, Non kadi varieties and hybrids of pumpkin were selected as **the object of research.**

The result of the experiment.

According to the results of the research, studies were conducted on the preparation of confectionery products by processing them in a sugary working solution during the preparation of ready-made candied fruit with added sugar from the raw materials of various varieties and hybrids of pumpkin. In the preparation of this candied fried product, the raw materials of varieties and hybrids of pumpkin are cut into four corners (cubic) and washed in ordinary clean water. Prepared samples of raw materials are placed in a working sugar solution and undergo a rest period for 12-14 hours. The pieces of pumpkin are treated at a temperature of 90 0C until the sugar paste is completely absorbed.

After the pieces of pumpkin change from light yellow color, that is, from their natural color, to dark color, the product becomes a primary finished product. The finished product will spend 40-50 minutes. The finished primary product is dried in a drying cabinet under laboratory conditions. During the drying process, parchment paper is laid on the bottom of the drying cabinet, and the pieces of pumpkin are cut out piece by piece. Then the diapers are placed in a drying cabinet and dried at a temperature of 40-50 0C. During the drying process, the duration of formation and the rate of formation of the product were analyzed. Samples are monitored every hour during drying of products in the drying cabinet. Products will be ready when the stickiness to the hand is partially reduced. It should be said that after the products are ready, the next technological process is carried out (Pic. 1).

Picture 1 shows the process of drying pumpkin slices in a drying cabinet and treating the dried products with powdered sugar.

Food products made from pumpkin are rich in important nutrients for the human body. It contains alpha-hydroxy acids (like glycolic and lactic acids) that slough off dead skin cells and give it a healthy glow. Pumpkin contains beta-carotene, vitamin A, which helps fight wrinkles. Zinc prevents acne and contributes to skin regeneration. Vitamin C contained in pumpkin increases immunity, and vitamin B improves blood circulation. Potassium, in turn, has a positive effect on hair health.

At the same time, the nutrients contained in pumpkin provide moisture to our hair and scalp, improve blood circulation and contribute to hair growth. In addition, antioxidants contained in pumpkin prevent damage to the scalp caused by free radicals. Therefore, it reduces the problem of hair loss.

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